

O'ZBEKISTONDA JAMOAT BINOLARI VA OLIY O'QUV YURTI BINOLARINING INTERERLARIDAGI MUAMMOLLAR

Ibragimov Murod Ismoiljonovich

"Arxitekturaviy loyixalash" kafedrasida katta oq'ituvchisi TAQU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7443233>

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqola Jamoat binolari va Oliy o'quv yurtlarining sinf xonalari, auditoriya, ma'ruza xonalari va boshqa xonalarini interer loyixalashdagi kamchiliklari ularda muammolar talabalarga va atrof muhitga salbiy ta'siri haqida ma'lumot beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Oliy o'quv yurtlari, interer, ranglar, bezak, yorqin, bezash, jixozlar.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИНТЕРЬЕРА ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫХ ЗДАНИЙ И ВУЗОВ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена информация о недостатках в оформлении интерьеров учебных аудиторий, аудиторий, аудиторий и других помещений общественных зданий и высших учебных заведений, а также о негативном влиянии проблем на обучающихся и окружающую среду.

Ключевые слова: Высшее учебное заведение, интерьер, цвета, убранство, яркое, убранство, оборудование.

PROBLEMS IN INTERIORS OF PUBLIC BUILDINGS AND HIGHER EDUCATION BUILDINGS IN UZBEKISTAN

Abstract. This article provides information about the shortcomings in the interior design of classrooms, auditoriums, lecture rooms and other rooms of public buildings and higher education institutions, and the negative impact of problems on students and the environment.

Keywords: Higher education institutions, interior, colors, decoration, bright, decoration, equipment.

KIRISH

O'quv yurti interyeri ham juda katta va muhim tarbiyaviy imkoniyatlarga ega bo'lgan muhit hisoblanadi, shuning uchun u yosh avlodni har tomonlama kamol toptirishga xizmat qilishi kerak. Birinchi galda, mavjud ta'limtarbiya metodlari va hozirgi zamon talablariga javob beradigan darajada badiiy bezatilmagan o'quv yurti interyerini har tomonlama maqsadga muvofiq deyish mumkin emas.

O'quv yurtida ta'limtarbiya ishlarining sifati, o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilarning yaxshi dam olishi hamda salomatligi o'quv yurti binosining ichki vazifaviy nuqtai nazardan maqsadga muvofiq xoldajihozlanishiga ham ma'lum darajada bog'liqdir. O'quv yurti interyeri o'quv xonasi, sinf xonalari, direktor xonasi, o'qituvchilar xonasi, oshxona bo'lishidan qat'i nazar, yuqorida aytilganidek, ta'lim-tarbiya ishlariga albatta ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Afsuski, ko'pincha interyerining o'quvchi shaxsi rivojlanishidagi ahamiyatiga yetarlicha e'tibor berilmaydi. Vaholanki, o'quvchining tushunchasiga ta'sir ko'rsatayotgan muhit uning ruhiy olamiga ham, atrof dagi narsalarga munosabatiga ham u yoki bu darajada ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Shuning uchun o'quvchilarni kamrab olgan muhitga, shu jumladan, maktab interyeriga ham tarbiyaning ajralmas qismi sifatida qarash lozim.

TADQIQOT MATERIALLARI VA METODOLOGIYASI

Interyerdagi har bir element: dam olish joyidagi kartina ham, xonalarning rangi ham, mebellarning shakli ham, xatto zinapoyalar xam o'quvchilar psixologiyasiga oz yoki ko'p ta'sir ko'rsatib, ularni atrof-muhitni idrok etishga, go'zallikni tushunishga o'rgatadi.

Ta'lim olayotgan 7 yoshdan 17 yoshgacha o'quvchilar asosan uch guruhga: kichik (1-IV sinflar), o'rta (V-VIII -sinflar) va katta (IXX) maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarga bo'linsa, ularning hammasi uchun o'ziga xos muhit kerak. Kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilar asosan bitta xonada shug'ullanadilar. O'rta yoshdagi o'quvchilarning ham o'zlariga birlashtirilgan xonasi bo'ladi. Lekin ular ayrim fanlar bo'yicha mashg'ulotlarni fan xonalarida o'tkazadilar. Katta yoshdagi o'quvchilar esa butunlay kabinet tizimiga o'tadilar.

Interyerdagi sinf xonalarini rejalashtirishda avvalo har qaysi guruh o'quvchilarning Mashg'ulotlari boshqa guruhlarga halaqit bermasligiga e'tibor berish lozim.

Masalan, boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari yuqori sinf o'quvchilaridan kam shug'ullanadi. Darslar ularning yosh xususiyatlaridan kelib chiqqan holda qisqartirilishi mumkin. Ayni vaqtda tanaffusga ajratilgan vaqt uzaytiriladi. Shuning uchun ularga alohida blok ajratilgani ma'qul.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI

Interyerni jihozlash va bezashda o'quvchilarning yoshini ham hisobga olish, ya'ni jihozlarni faqat muayyan yoshdagi o'quvchilarning bo'yiga mosligini emas, balki turli yosh guruhidagi bolalarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini ham nazarda tutishiga e'tibor berish lozim. Keyingi paytlarda o'quv yurtlari tipovoy loyihalar bo'yicha kurilmokda.

Bu binolarning rejalashtirilishi deyarli bir xil. Shuning uchun ularni jihozlash va bezashda interyerlarning o'ziga xos bo'lishiga erishish juda muhimdir.

O'quv yurtida o'rganiladigan fanlarning mazmunidan qa'ti nazar, ta'limning bir necha shakl va metodlari mavjud bo'lib, bular o'quv xonalarining jihozlari va ularning joylashuvini belgilaydi. Bunda turli omillar qatori o'quvchilarning yoshiga xos psixologik-fiziologik xususiyatlari ham nazarda tutiladi. Ta'limning asosiy shakllari jamoa, guruh va yakka tartibdagi mashg'ulotlardir».

Interyerlarning zamon talablari darajasidagi jihozlari va badiiy bezaklari o'quvchilarni estetik tarbiyalashda, ularning tasavvuri ham didini rivojlantirishda yordam berishi kerak maktab interyerini badiiy bezashda tasviriy san'atning monumental va dekorativ haykaltaroshlik, yog'och va ganch o'ymakorligi, mozika kabi turlari keng qo'llanilmokda.

O'quvchilarning o'zlarini ana shu ishlarga jalb etish eng avvalo ularda o'quv yurti binosiga, undagi jihozlarni va bezaklarga ehtiyotkorona munosabatni tarbiyalashda pedagoglarga katta yordam beradi.

Zamonaviy me'morlik namunalari interyerdagi barcha elementlarning uslubiy birligi bilan ajralib turadi. Interyerni garmonik hal qilish undagi elementlar

REFERENCES

1. Adilovna, Q. S. (2021). Features of the Design of Public Buildings in the Organization of Public Services. *湖南大学学报(自然科学版)*, 48(10).
2. Ozadovich, K. A., & Ismailovich, I. B. (2021). Issues of Organization of Service Sets on the Uzbek National Highway A-380. *Design Engineering*, 2582-2586.
3. Inogamov, B. I., & Khasanov, A. O. (2021). Taking Into Account Socio-Functional Factors in the Design of Housing. *Design Engineering*, 2587-2589.

4. Yunusov, S. H., & Qodirova, S. A. (2021). Issues Related to National Forms in the Architecture of Uzbekistan. *Design Engineering*, 10940-10943.
5. Adilovna, Q. S., & Ozodovich, X. A. (2021). REQUIREMENTS FOR THE PREPARATION OF INTERIORS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 2(11), 74-77.
6. Ramatov, J., & Umarova, R. (2021). Central Asia in IX-XII Centuries: Socio-political Situation, Spiritual and Cultural Development. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 2(04), 148-151.
7. Qodirova, S. A., Aripova, N. A., Raximov, L. S., Turebaev, J. O., & Abdusalomov, U. X. (2021). Requirements For The Formation Of The Historical Structure And Internal Environment Of Secondary Schools. *The American Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 3(04), 60-64.
8. Qodirova, S. A., Raximov, L. S., Allayorov, K. O., & Sodiqov, M. M. (2021). Peculiarities Of The Buildings Of The Cultural And Educational Center. *The American Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 3(03), 1-6.
9. Abdujabbarova, M., Nazarenko, T., Begmatova, D., & Tuxtayeva, M. (2021). Industrial Production Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan. *The American Journal of Applied sciences*, 3(11), 39-47.
10. Xushnazavovich, Q. R., Xammatovna, S. M., & Mirkamol o'g'li, S. M. (2021). Traditional Houses and Architecture of Kashkadarya. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630)*, 12, 459-463.
11. Khasanov, A. O., & Allayorov, K. O. (2021). Residential Yurts Of The Ancient Nomads Of Central Asia And The Use Of Yurts In Tourism. *The American Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 3(01), 58-64.
12. Adilovna, Q. S. (2021). THE LINK OF CULTURAL AND EDUCATIONAL CENTERS TO THE SOLUTION OF THE PROJECT IDEA. *Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL)*, 2(11), 92-95.
13. Ozodovich, X. A., Iqramovich, A. R., & Shaxnazarovich, R. L. (2021). Location of auxiliary rooms inside the living rooms in bukhara traditional residential areas.
14. Khasanov, A. (2020). Organizing Eco Tourism Along With Uzbek National Automagistrale Way. *Solid State Technology*, 63(6), 12674-12678.
15. Khasanov, A. (2016). About several infrastructure constructions of the Great Silk Road. *Int'l J Innov Sci Eng Technol*, 3(6), 295-299.
16. Ozodovich, X. A., & Azim o'g'li, N. A. (2021). Formation of the "Obod Mahalla" System in the Villages of Uzbekistan and Serving the Population. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMYIY JURNALI*, 1(5), 325-329.
17. Inogamov, B. I., & Khasanov, A. O. (2021). Taking Into Account Socio-Functional Factors in the Design of Housing. *Design Engineering*, 2587-2589.
18. Ozodovich, H. A., & Maribovich, Q. I. (2022). Improving the Design of Youth Innovative-Creative and Development Scientific Centers. *Eurasian Scientific Herald*, 7, 72-76.
19. TACI, A. K. About Several Infrastructure Constructions Of The Great Silk Road.
20. Mahmudov, O. Z. O., & Kasimov, I. M. (2021). THE STUDY OF THE GEOECOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF A BIG CITY. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(4), 271-275.

21. Раззаков, С. Ж., Холбоев, З. Х., & Косимов, И. М. (2020). Определение динамических характеристик модели зданий, возведенных из малопрочных материалов.
22. Zokirjon o'g'li, M. O., & Kasimov, I. M. (2021). MODELING OF BUILDINGS. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(05), 772-781.
23. Dedakhanov, B., & Kasimov, I. (2022). ANCIENT ARCHITECTURE OF THE FERGHANA VALLEY FEATURES OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT (ON THE EXAMPLE OF CIVIL ARCHITECTURE AND URBAN PLANNING). *Science and innovation*, 1(C6), 278-284.
24. Ravshanovich, A. Z. (2021). Issues Of Improving Tourism Opportunities In Namangan Region. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 26(2), 40-44.
25. Ozodovich, H. A., & Maribovich, Q. I. (2022). Improving the Design of Youth Innovative-Creative and Development Scientific Centers. *Eurasian Scientific Herald*, 7, 72-76.